

APPENDIX 1

“Tasks Management”

A PROJECT REPORT

Submitted by

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in partial fulfillment for the award of the degree
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IN

COMPUTER SCIENCE AND ENGINEERING

PRIYADARSHINI COLLEGE OF ENGINEERING
RASHTRASANT TUKDOJI MAHARAJ NAGPUR UNIVERSITY
Session 2021-22

APPENDIX 2

PRIYADARSHINI COLLEGE OF ENGINEERING, NAGPUR
Department of Computer Science and Engineering

CERTIFICATE

Certified that this project report “**Tasks Management**” is the bonafide work of “**Mousmi Uikey, Divya Shrivastava, Vandana Upase, Vrushabh Kelwadkar, Sahil Meshram** ” from 7th Semester carried out the project work under my supervision.

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APPENDIX 3

DECLARATION

I hereby declare that the project entitled “**Tasks Management**” submitted for the B. E. (Computer Science and Engineering) degree is our original work and the project has not formed the basis for the award of any other degree, diploma, fellowship or any other similar titles.

Signature of the Students

Semester: 8th

Place: Nagpur

Date:

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

A. Project Specification:

- There is a rapid growth of small firm, And As a start up they lacks some resources or we can also say there are lots of communication barrier which create lots of problem to complete the tasks,meet deadlines, updates and works which directly affect the completion of work and the reputation of the firm simultaneously.
- In Research we found that in small firm the works are done using mails so every time while distributing the tasks the manager or admin have to find out their email-id and share there tasks with them.Since this the only mean they can use to keep a track and communicate all their employees on the organization level .
- Sometimes,it happen that the employee received this mail but they forgets to recheck their mail box and perform only the tasks,they have check this is nothing but a result of a communication barrier.
- Apart from this all it is seen that while using mail and whatsapp for allocation of tasks there are many security risks.
- Some other case studies shows that during the time of allocation of tasks to a specific employee the admin and manager get confused between same name an role of the employee and send the tasks to the wrong employee who is not responsible for that works and this can create a misunderstanding between them and delay as well.
- When we have done more deep study we come to known that many time important documents were misplaced or get lost in lots of mails and documents. And it result in difficulties to research that documents.so to overcome this scenario we have introduced our module know as Tasks Management.
- Tasks Management is a bridge that will play the role of a communication between employer, manager, and employees and reduced the risks on losing or forgetting important tasks.It will also make it easy to assess all the tasks to the employees.
- Tasks Management makes accessing and sharing all your tasks easy as it's can works on any device such as laptop, handset,PC etc. So people can access it from anywhere and any time.
- The programming language we used for building Tasks Management application (App) is java and android studio, HTML kotlin.
- Accessing the Tasks Management app is easy and it not unlike the traditional mailing system in which you have to write the mail id of every employees again and again. Here, the admin will already have a separate and unique mail id of each and every employees which is personally make by them.They just have to select the mail id or the name they have make and a new screen will appeared in which they will just enter the task.
- We found that there are many mail a person receive in their mail box everyday and many time some important mail are found in spam or mail. So, increase the possibility that are important mail of client or employer is missed to create a problem for firm and employee.
- So this app will not only helps in the small firm industry but also in the education purpose in school and colleges. So that the employers, teacher and the employees and students can easily allocate the tasks and access it.

B. Literature survey

- Google Classroom- classroom application of google in which the teacher assigned all the assignments to the students and then the students access the takes complete it and can easily upload it.
- Stacks- Trello is the collaborative app to tackle team through note card lists, board etc. In which one can easily take the photo of the documents and then the app stacks that documents into corrects categories like billing, banking , insurances, medical, tax, travel tickets, works etc

- Spike – Is a revolutionary approach to how communication and collaboration happen in 2020 & beyond. By combining email calendar , notes , task , and to-do list. It create manage & share to do list directly form. It access all your personal account with one simple unified inbox.
- Toodledo -Is an incredibly powerful tool to increase your productivity and organize your life. It make customs to do list etc. It provide you with a place to write longs notes, make custom lists, create structure outline and tracks your habits.
- Whatsapp - An application in which you can easily chats and share and receive all our important documents, photos, location etc. It is a kind of messaging with the advanced feature of sharing and receiving documents ,photos along with the facilities of video call and phone calls.
- Google Tasks - Is a mobile application that capture, manage and edits your tasks from anywhere, at anytime, with to do lists that sync your devices. It is integrated with Gmail and Google Calender so that you can complete your tasks faster.
- Taskade - Is a all in one collaboration platform for remote teams. It unleash your teams productivity with tasks list,mindmaps and video calls ou can manage it anytime and anywhere with plan collaboration.

CHAPTER 2

ANALYSIS AND DESIGN

A. Requirement Analysis

Tasks Management is a board programming is a brilliant answer for focus on undertakings, oversee time, and comply with time constraints. The apparatuses and applications for task the board will save you from with nothing to do for getting sorted out tacky notes, looking through messages and applications for tasks, and sorting out what to chip away from the start. Save time and stay on schedule by delegating and tracking tasks. Say goodbye to losing work or scrambling to track down information. Task tracking allows teams to see which tasks are most important or time intensive. ... Easily assign tasks to team members.

Small companies don't have such software so we are building an application which can help them as well. Here are the reasons for integration of such software.

a) Improves Collaboration and Coordination

Probably the greatest advantage of an undertaking the board device is it further develops joint effort between different intra and between departmental groups that work to achieve a typical assignment. Regardless of whether the undertaking is huge or little, every colleague has a specific job and obligation. For a smooth execution and ideal organization of the venture, it is basic to guarantee that each part remains inside associated.

b) Enhances Planning and Execution

Arranging is crucial for save time and exertion. For each venture advancement cycle, project arranging assumes a fundamental part. The undertaking the board programming can empower administrators to allocate errands to various colleagues according to their abilities and execute the venture appropriately. Project arranging needs a great deal of time as the group needs to layout every one of the significant stages. The assignment the board instrument empowers the administration to decide the request for undertakings.

c) Facilitates Resource Allocation

The administration thinks that it is hard to allot assets according to the intricacy of assignments and capacities of assets. It is important to oversee assets proficiently to guarantee smooth achievements of business processes.

d) Strengthens Team Work flow

e) Maintain security

f) Continuous Monitoring and maintain security

CHAPTER 3

PROJECT DESCRIPTION

A. Design of propose of work

Tasks Management is consisting of different frames works. It's a plask screen when one open the application when last foe 2 to3 seconds and then enter in the main section where our main application menu are present. Here there are 3 card view presents. This card views as admin, Manager and employees.

The user is going to used this card view option to login in the app as per there position in the organization the belong like the admin is going to enter in the employees or manager section to assigned there tasks to them and sometime even to monitor that are tasks and works assigned to the employees are right or not. And the same is happen with the employees and manager section. They will login in the app and look after there task and works and then work according to it.

Tasks Management filled in fame throughout the long term and has advanced altogether enveloping all the more remarkable elements. You can make, coordinate and focus on errands, make sub-tasks and conditions just as make projects and sub-projects.

You can name assignments, redo through shading codes, and add due dates to monitor the errands. An unmistakable element that accompanies Tasks Management is the AI-fueled element known as Smart Schedule.

Through Smart Schedule, the application recommends ideal dates for planning and rescheduling existing undertakings.

- Tasks Management work on following modules.

- Admin
- Manager
- Employee

- **Admin:-** Owner of firm or office having authority to create Id password of manager, employee and provide task or note Admin is the one responsible to make a different and unique ID/Password for the employees and the manager of the firm.

- **Manager:-**Manager are the one which are responsible to make sure that the tasks is assigned to the right person with same name or with same work position based on the different department. Manager also have authority to register new employee and provide them the task with respect to the old or already register employees in he company database.

- **Employee:-**The manager assigned the password and Unique mail ID made b the firm to the employees using which the employee is going to login in the system and can easily access their ask using the application. The employees can login in as many time they want to checks the list of tasks they have been assigned.

B. Data Flow Diagram

CHAPTER 4

PROJECT IMPLEMENTATION

A. Develops Collaboration and Coordination:

Likely the best benefit of an endeavor the board gadget is it further creates joint exertion between various intra and between departmental gatherings that work to accomplish a common task. Whether or not the endeavor is immense or little, every partner has a particular work and commitment. For a smooth execution and ideal association of the endeavor, it is essential to ensure that each part stays inside related.

B. Improves Planning and Execution

Orchestrating is essential for save time and effort. For each adventure progression cycle, project organizing expects an essential part. The endeavor the board programming can engage overseers to dispense tasks to different partners as per their capacities and execute the endeavor fittingly. Project organizing needs a lot of time as the gathering needs to format all of the critical stages. The task the board instrument enables the organization to choose the solicitation for endeavors.

C. Strengthens teams works

Keeping the whole group in a circle is a serious assignment, however the undertaking the executives apparatus simplifies it. The instrument can go about as a stage that unites each colleague and makes them cooperate. The undertaking chief can without much of a stretch track the exercises of different colleagues and actually take a look at the ongoing place of doled out errands.

D. Maintain security:

The app is highly secured as everyone as there own password and user id that is unique. And even if one login in the phone or PC of someone else after sometime you need to login in again if ou exit out or stay active for a long time, So here in this app there is system of login in and out every time you feel to checks your tasks. Because of this no one else can checks our tasks with them. And maintain the security at the same time confidential information, security, and privacy.

E. Continuous monitoring of employees

Ventures need to follow the presentation of the task at each stage to get long haul achievement and guarantee on-time conveyance. The errand the board device screens each assignment to accomplish this goal consistently. The organization the board can likewise bring execution information of each colleague and constantly screens each phase of the undertaking through this instrument. It helps the organization to improve every one of the tasks viably.

CHAPTER 5

SCREENSHOT

CHAPTER 6

ADVANTAGES & APPLICATION

A. Advantages

- It makes faster development and track every activity of the employee for small IT firms.
- Accessible from anywhere and anytime
- Target multiple platforms can make employees target clear.
- we can add or improve old features and task given to the employee.
- Create, assign, organize, prioritize and share tasks.
- Schedule recurring meetings.
- Create and schedule recurring tasks.
- Manage tasks and to do lists with home Boards.
- Create and assign projects.
- Select from multiple statuses for a task.
- Alerts, notifications, and reminders to keep teams on track.
- Maintain privacy ,integrity, confidential tasks, and security

B. Application

With its simplified, user-friendly GUI letting you navigate a powerful set of features, Tasks Management stands out of the crowd when it comes to helping with task completion. You can make assignments and sub-tasks and plan them as single-time, or repeating undertakings. Through agendas, you can list down what to be finished. In addition, you can make undertakings and partner various assignments under them. You can sort out, focus on undertakings and screen task status.

Choices, for example, progress reports, timetables, and Gantt Charts let you keep projects on target. Tasks Management assists you with saving time with incredible inquiry and channel choices. You can look for errands, tasks, gatherings, and do parts more. Furthermore, there are pre-saved channels to save time and exertion on the end-clients part.

CHAPTER 7

CONCLUSION & FUTURE SCOPE

A. Conclusion

- Maintain the security principle which are integrity, confidentiality and privacy
- Consist of to do list for the employees and update the list on it's own when a new tasks is provided.
- It is access anywhere and anytime since it is also work on mobile phone
- Admin manager can send their task from this application by just clicking on their name and after that employee can see his task on his mobile phone.
- Easily task can be given to employees and they can be edited or added.

An element rich undertaking the executives instrument offers many advantages for present day endeavors going from improving work process to upgrading usefulness that outcomes in expanded ROI over the period. All you want to choose a dependable and future-prepared errand the board application that your representatives acknowledge and use effortlessly.

Tasks Management is an altered undertaking the executives apparatus that empowers your venture to deal with all assignments effectively in this pained time and even in the post-COVID age. Our vigorous errand the board application assist associations with confronting difficulties identified with project the executives and gain a higher ROI over the period while fulfilling the time constraints and using assets viably.

B. Future scope

- Expandable memory & runs on affordable large devices.
- Supports running multiple apps simultaneously
- Supports cloud storage enabling sync of devices with G-account.
- Supports 3rd party widget & information display on screen.
- To keep the track of employees entry time and out time.
- Display the bonus and employee details all together, which can even support different services of Microsoft of 3rd party app for conversation.

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